

INDICATORS OF THE STUDENTS ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN IKERE LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF EKITI – STATE.

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the indicators of the students academic performance in English language in junior secondary school one (JSS1) with a view to finding out ways to improve the students' performance in English language. The survey research design was adopted for the study. The sample consisted of 20 secondary schools in Ikere Local Government Area of Ekiti State. Stratified and simple random sampling procedures were used to select 330 respondents used for the study. Structured questionnaire was utilized for the data collection. Two research hypotheses were raised and analyzed using simple frequency counts, percentages and chi-square at 0.05 level of significance. Results of the findings revealed that the teacher's attitude affects the students' performance in English language TR HPO 1(cal. $X^2= 440.82$ Table value = 36.42, df= 24, $P<0.05$ ST HPO 1: Cal. $X^2= 285.8$, Table = 26.30, df= 12, $P<0.05$). Availability and usage of instructional materials affects students' performance in English language TR HPO 2. (Cal. $X^2 =277.57$, Table value = 15.51, df= 8 $P<0.05$ ST HPO II: Cal $X^2=332.4$, t value =26, df=16, $P<0.05$). Each hypothesis was tested at 0.05 alpha levels. In conclusion, it was shown that teachers' attitude, the availability and usage of instructional materials and students' attitude are some of the indicators of the performances of students in English language.

KEYWORDS: Academic performance, English language, Junior secondary school, Students' attitude

INTRODUCTION

Following extensive research, several researchers have suggested different approaches to the inculcation of the study of English in the child. Nattall (1992) analyzed some of the indicators of performance of students in English language at the secondary school level. He also asserted that there was no single cause but a combination of adverse indicators which are interrelated. These indicators include; teacher's factors, school environment, technological needs/ instructional materials, interference of mother tongue, readiness in learning, visual and auditory skills, and curriculum implementation.

These indicators to the teaching and learning of English language at the secondary school have become a sensitive issue that should be taken with seriousness. In view of the foregoing in the educational programme of the country the study was to examine the teacher's factors, the usage of adequate instructional materials vis-à-vis organizing instructions, which can facilitates productive teaching and learning since the teacher was the greatest indicator of academic performance of students in the teaching and learning of English language in the secondary schools.

Olugbodi (2006) asserted that Teachers are producers of knowledge, by teaching the learners one additional language besides their mother tongues. They should know the different kinds of problems and how these affect the intellectual, social, emotional and cultural lives of their students. There is also the need to have knowledge of the pupils' cultural backgrounds as they attempt to teach them new language.

Olugbodi (2003) also stated that teachers are required to make students become more balanced through teaching and setting of high goals regarding competence in the language to be learnt. The teacher should be a good model and should let the learners really use the language to achieve communicative competence.

Azikwe (1998) affirmed that the development of the ability to learn the second language was one of the most important responsibilities of the language teacher. English language competence was important because it was essential to personal enrichment and the development of intelligent citizenship. Having known linguistic, cultural, socio-linguistic, political and psychological problems of English language the teacher should be in a

better position to reduce these problems. He should not set unrealistic objectives. Offorma (1990) stated that the teacher should encourage the learners to have positive attitude in learning English language. This was because the matter of attitude could enhance or inhibit level of proficiency. Adeyanju (1988) affirmed that the world was getting smaller day by day. Therefore, there was need for changes in our approaches in the teaching of language. To choose any method at all, the teacher should consider the learners, environment, instructional materials and objectives of learning the language. Classroom teachers must study the methods to have a pragmatic attitude i.e. which one is relevant and which is not.

Brain (2002) stated that student learning could be affected by the chosen method of instruction by the individual teachers and the way they go about the task. For example, teachers vary in the style of teaching they adopt in their classes and this could influence students' performance. Babikko (2002) asserted that teachers have different expectations and attitudes towards their students and this could lead to labeling and stereo-typing. These actions have a dramatic effect on the students' performance during the class instruction. He advised the teachers to make their teaching on student centered method that focused on learning skill rather than on the subject matter. Also, Olugbodi (2006) affirmed that unfortunately, the teacher was the victim of all the poor planning and implementation of education programmes. This was a reflection of the teacher's status. He was not respected by the government. He was ordered around on errands meant for office attendants, used as enumerator during censuses, polling agent for the politicians at the election periods and traffic warden to await the arrival of top politicians on the busy roads on very sunny or rainy days. He asserted that which other profession suffered such humiliation? However, teacher is a key factor in the education programmes i.e. in the school system.

Olugbodi (2006) stated that the ability to use English language enhances both horizontal and vertical mobility of people, because of the prestige attached to the language even if such a person is literate in the mother tongue. Alonge (2003) asserted that English language is the language of the institutions e.g. education, technology, administration, judiciary and executive. The business of all these institutions is still largely conducted in the language, that is, English.

The use of instructional materials entails a deep and professional understanding of the relationship between the technical- know how to and of the use of the instructional objectives of the learning process. Generally, many teachers are faced with the task of applying these materials to various classroom learning activities. Again, many under- utilized this perhaps, leads to the poor achievement level of students.

According to Alo (2003), teachers are expected to select and use instructional materials which will enable the learners master the desired objectives. In other words, the material in question has specific objectives it can attain in order to assist the learning process. Berge and Chike- Okoli (2002) noticed that the first basic requirement for the effective utilization of any educational material was the awareness of the existence of such materials by the target audience. i. e. it should be brought to the notice of concerned learners.

Ofodu (2004) stated that the use of instructional materials, aimed at simplifying teaching for effective learning. Therefore, the material should not be complicated thereby sending the learners into the realm of abstract thinking.

Mohammed (1995) in his own view, observed that students' proficiency in English as measured by WAEC seemed to be declining rapidly, particularly since the failure rate in the last five years has been in the region of 70- 75% annually.

Awonusi (2004), noticed that secondary schools with qualified and specialist teachers usually produce the best students in terms of academic performance and communicative competence.

Katcha (1997) stated that the level of training the teacher has been exposed to in the useful application of instructional media during English lessons would affect the performance of the learners. By implication, it is clear that the teacher will produce students like himself.

Aiyepku (2006) observed that learning facilities are indispensable in the learning process. It was universally agreed that adequate instructional facilities enhances students' performance in academic pursuits, whereas, their deficiency detracted greatly from the quality education. He posited that adequate learning materials will bring about increment in students' level of performance.

Umeh (2002) studied the utilization of the language laboratory for teaching oral English as a means of enhancing the learners' performance. His focus was on the idea that skills of oracy should be practiced in a language laboratory which was designed to provide an atmosphere conducive for learner to master them. However, he went further to link the poor oral competence and academic performance of learners to the scarce nature of language laboratories in our secondary schools.

In addition, it was discovered by the researcher that some students could not read to understand texts, to discuss issues in English, and consequently, could not answer questions appropriately in English language examinations.

The study highlights the indicators of students' performance in English language in the secondary schools. The study is also of great value to the performance of students in English language. It is also assumed that the study will trigger off further research on the topic not only at secondary level but also in the tertiary institutions.

Therefore, the outcome of this research should be a tool for government agencies, school boards, Ministries of Education, School Administration and teachers in the selection of suitable indicators that will enhance the students' performance in English language in the secondary schools.

Research Hypothesis:

1. There is no significant relationship between the teachers' attitude and students' performance in English language.
2. There is no significant relationship between the availability and usage of instructional materials and the students' performance in English language.

METHODOLOGY

The survey research design was adopted for the study. Ten (10) secondary schools were randomly selected for the study. Three (3) teachers and thirty students from each school were used. The total numbers of teachers used were thirty (30) and three hundred students, and they all responded. Teachers and students were randomly selected from the selected secondary schools.

The instrument used for data collection was structured questionnaire. A 30 item statement on the indicators of academic performance of students in English language in the Junior Secondary schools was constructed. This was a likert type questionnaire with five point scale specially developed for this study; it was tagged "scale of indicators of academic performance of students in English language" (IAPSEL).

The first part of the questionnaire elicited responses about the background of the teachers and students. The second part investigated the indicators of academic performance of students in English language. The questionnaire was utilized for the data collection, using simple frequency counts, percentages and chi-square to analyze the collected data and the research hypothesis formulated.

Objectives

This study set out to:

1. Find out the indicators of students' performance in English language.
2. Examine if the indicators when looked into, will improve the performance of students in English language.
3. Investigate the performance of the students and make suggestions..

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Hypothesis 1: there is no significant relationship between the teachers' attitude and students' academic performance as indicator of student academic performance in English language.

Table 1a: Chi-square table of responses of teachers to the teachers' attitude and students' academic performance as indicator of student academic performance in English language.

Observed Frequencies											
S/N	Question items	SA	A	N	DA	SD	TOTAL	X ² _c	X ² _t	Df	Decision
	I always read books and journals to widen my knowledge	43	41	50	64	92	300			24	HO is rejected
	I adopt different methods during my teaching	102	67	41	50	40	300	440.82	36.42		
	I cannot cover the syllabus before the examination	107	94	12	50	37	300				
	I give adequate test to evaluate students	105	84	15	46	50	300				
	I allow students full participation in my lesson	90	70	26	70	44	300				
	I skip over areas of my difficulties	40	37	26	78	119	300				
	English language is not given enough time on the time table	98	86	30	40	46	300				

P>0.05

Cal. X²=440.82, Table value=36.42 df= 24 at 0.05 level of significance.

KEY

SA – Strongly Agree, A – Agreed, N – Neutral, DA –Disagreed, SD – Strongly Disagreed

From Table 1a, it could be seen that X²_c is 440.82, while X²_t is 36.42. Since X²_c is greater than X²_t, the stated hypothesis is rejected. In other words, there is a significant relationship in the teacher's attitude and students' academic performance as indicator of student academic performance in English language.

Table 1b: Chi-square Table on Students' Responses on Teachers' attitude and Students' performance in English language

Observed Frequencies											
S/N	Question items	SA	A	N	DA	SD	TOTAL	X ² _c	X ² _t	Df	Decision
	My teacher's attitude towards the students during English lesson encourages me	84	66	25	65	60	300	285.8	26.30	12	HO rejected
	My teacher allows me to participate freely and actively during the teaching of English	114	55	46	46	61	300				
	My teacher is not a specialist in English	87	43	28	40	102	300				
	My teacher does not come to class regularly	25	82	15	68	112	300				

P>0.05

Cal.X²= 285.8, Table value= 26.30 at 0.05 level of significance.

From Table1b, it could be seen that the X²_t is 285.8 while the X²_t is 26.30. Since the X²_c is greater than the X²_t the stated hypothesis was rejected. In other words, there was a significant relationship between the teacher's attitudes and students' academic performance as indicator of student academic performance in English language.

Table 1b shows that chi-sequence calculated value of 285.8 is greater than the critical value of 26.30 was significant as 0.05 alpha levels. This initiates that there was a significant relationship between the teacher's attitude and students' academic performance as indicator of student academic performance in English language. In essence, null hypothesis was rejected.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship in the availability and usage of instructional materials as indicator of students' academic performance in English language.

From Table 2a, it could be seen that X^2_c is 277.57 while $X^2_t = 15.51$. Since the X^2_c is greater than X^2_t , the stated hypothesis is rejected. In other words, there is a significant relationship in the availability and usage of instructional materials as indicator of the students' academic performance in English language.

TABLE 2a: Chi Square Table on Teachers' Responses on Availability and Usage of Instructional Materials

		Observed Frequencies						X^2_c	X^2_t	df	Decision
S/N	Question Items	SA	A	N	DA	SD	TOTAL				
1	I always use adequate instruction materials to supplement my teaching	115	47	30	98	80	300			8	HO is rejected
2	The library is well equipped with English textbooks	40	31	30	82	117	300	277.57	15.51		
3	English language is difficult for students because there are no language laboratories in schools.	108	82	20	46	44	300				

$P > 0.05$

Cal. $X^2 = 277.57$, Table value = 15.51 at 0.05 level of significance.

TABLE 2b: Chi Square Table on Students' Responses on Availability and Usage of Instructional Materials

		Observed Frequencies						X^2_c	X^2_t	Df	decision
S/N	Question Items	SA	A	N	DA	SD	TOTAL				
	There are no adequate and relevant teaching aids for the teaching of English	84	70	22	60	64	300			16	HO is rejected
	students should be involved in the selected of textbooks	124	62	19	40	55	300	332.4	26.30		
	English language is difficult for the students because the school has no library	95	70	20	55	60	300				
	English language is difficult because there are no language laboratories to teach the spoke aspect of the language	109	60	33	48	50	300				
	I do not like English because my teacher does not use instructional materials to teach.	106	92	30	30	42	300				

$P > 0.05$

Cal. $X^2 = 332.4$, t value = 26.30 at 0.05 at level of significance

From Table 2b, it could be seen that X^2_c is greater than X^2_t , the stated hypothesis is rejected. In other words, there was no significant relationship between availability and usage of instructional materials as indicator of student academic performance.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The result of the hypothesis shows a significant relationship in the finding of study that teachers' attitude was one of the most indicator of students performance in English According to Adeyanju (1998), the teacher was a key factor in the learning system. His orientation and commitments towards learning can trigger students for better learning. This also was in line with the findings of Alo (2003) that the worst mistake a teacher can make was to think only of the subject as it was shown on the class time table not minding the success a student must make under his / her teaching process. The result shows that teachers' attitude is very important to the performance of students in the teaching of English.

Adeosun (2003) asserted that teachers' attitude on learning was very much important if maximum values are to be derived from English learning. The teacher must fully prepare his / her lesson before coming to the class. The teachers' method of teaching, attitude and personality have a great influence on the students' performance, therefore, teachers must be friendly with the students.

Results for hypothesis 2 shows that there was a significant relationship in the study that the availability and the usage of instructional materials as indicator of students' academic performance in English Language.

Hence, the inadequacies of instructional materials can hinder the teaching and learning of English. Most secondary schools in Ekiti State are over- populated, ill- equipped with irrelevant and outdated libraries.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

All the hypotheses tested proved that junior secondary school students' academic performance in English language is a function of teachers' attitude, availability and usage of instructional materials.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made as new challenges, for other researchers in the field to focus on the careful study of more specific questions such as:

1. Further studies should consider effects of teachers' attitudes and students' performance in English language. Since teachers are the transmitters, transformers, reformers and facilitators of knowledge, they and school administrators are responsible for creating the enabling environment to assist students in cultivating a healthy attitude if desired objectives are to be achieved.
2. Availability and usage of instructional materials, their identification, location and economic value should be focused on the studies of English. Since instructional materials help to motivate and improve students' attitude towards learning.
3. There should be proper monitoring of the students while teaching.
4. Teachers should be able to improvise using as many instructional materials as possible to enhance the students' performance.
5. Teachers should make learning environment more conducive, interesting, fascinating and friendly with learners.
6. The students should make themselves available in the classroom regularly and punctually.
7. Curriculum developers should be more innovative in developing curriculum materials such as textbooks, teacher's guide, syllabus e. t. c. that would be more flexible to accommodate teachers' innovative and creative ideas.

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